

Towards seamless automation in multimodal transport and logistics

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Abstract

As global supply chains become progressively more complex and demands for rapid delivery continuously increase, the need for innovative solutions in freight transport and logistics has never been more critical. The introduction of automation appears as a promising way to address these challenges. However, in most applications so far, the development of automation is fragmented across different transport modes and operations environments (i.e. ports, hubs, warehouses), hindering interoperability and the realization of end-to-end automated logistics. The objective of this paper is to identify the benefits as well as the challenges posed by the use of automation in multimodal freight transport and logistics and to introduce a new open reference architecture framework for digital twins, one of the most prominent emerging technologies in the field. Four use cases are employed to extract relevant user needs, understand technological gaps, and to validate the proposed reference architecture at a later stage. The framework acts as a critical enabler for the use cases, as it guides the implementation of essential functionalities in port automation, logistics optimization, and real-time visualization. This way, it lays the foundation for transforming port operations, streamlining logistics networks, and enhancing supply chain visibility. The research presented herein opens interesting pathways towards achieving seamless integration of automated processes across the end-to-end logistics chain using different transport modes.

Keywords: Data sharing and interoperability, multimodal transport, automation, digital twin

Introduction

The European transport sector is a critical economic driver, contributing approximately 5% to the EU's GDP and employing over 10 million people (European Commission, 2024). Freight transport is essential for regional growth and competitiveness and plays a crucial role in supply chain management by facilitating the efficient movement and timely delivery of raw materials as well as complete products (Crainic et al., 2009). The geographic separation between producers and consumers drives the demand for freight transportation (He et al., 2018). As trade has become more and more globalized, traditional road transport has become less practical, and its negative impact on sustainability has been increasingly recognized (e.g. see Nkesah, 2023; Santos et al.,

2010), making the exploration of alternative modes of transportation and their combinations essential.

Rising freight demand combined with existing capacity constraints has intensified the negative externalities associated with transportation, including air, noise and visual pollution, congestion, accidents and excessive CO₂ emissions that contribute to climate change (Serrano-Hernández et al., 2017; Demir et al., 2015). These issues have harmful impacts on the economy, public health, and overall quality of life (International Transport Forum, 2021). The importance of efficient and effective transportation is thus becoming evident, as transportation costs constitute a substantial portion of the overall supply chain expenses. As global supply chains become progressively more complex and demands for rapid delivery continuously increase, the need for innovative solutions in freight transport and logistics has never been more critical (Tavasszy, 2020).

The introduction of automation appears as a promising way to address these challenges. For a systematic literature review on the application of automation in logistics see Ferreira and Reis (2023) and for further insights on how automation impacts sustainable development in general see Almusharraf (2025). Terminals and hubs offer ideal controlled environments for the implementation of advanced automation technologies aiming at improving efficiency and capacity. Nevertheless, in most applications so far, the development of automation is fragmented across different transport modes, hindering interoperability and the realization of end-to-end automated logistics. The seamless movement of goods from origin to destination would require integrated operational models and extensive data sharing between different automated systems. Therefore, to fully benefit from the potential of automation, the key would be to follow a more coordinated approach in order to bridge the gaps in how automation is introduced and handled among different transport modes, towards a seamlessly integrated freight and logistics system.

In this direction, the objective of this paper is to identify the benefits as well as the challenges posed by the use of automation in multimodal freight transport and logistics and to introduce a new open reference architecture framework for digital twins, one of the most prominent emerging technologies in the field. Four use cases are employed to extract relevant user needs, understand technological gaps, and to validate the proposed reference architecture in a later stage. The use cases refer to different parts of the freight transport and logistics chain, namely; automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels, automated port operations, automated shunting as a service oriented platform, automated multimodal terminal operations.

The paper is mainly based on the on-going research conducted in the context of the AutoMoTIF¹ (Automation towards multimodal transport and integration of freight) project, funded by the Horizon Europe Programme (GA: 101147693)². The remainder of the paper is structured as follows; initially, the state-of-the-art in automation in multimodal freight transport is presented, focusing on benefits, challenges and barriers, as well as on the role of emerging technologies. Following that, the new proposed open reference architecture approach is introduced and the four use cases are presented. The paper concludes with some insights on how the proposed

¹ <https://automotif-project.eu/>

² Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

reference architecture can be used to move towards seamless automation in multimodal freight transport and logistics.

Automation in multimodal freight transport: Benefits, challenges, barriers and emerging technologies

The modal split of freight transport in the EU, based on tonne-km, shows that maritime transport accounts for almost 68% of freight transport performance, followed by road transport with 25%. Rail transport represented only a 5.5 %, inland waterways 1.6 % and air 0.2 % (2022 data based on tonne-km) (Eurostat, 2022). As freight transport continues to grow, road freight transport is projected to increase by around 40% by 2030 and by little over 80% by 2050 (European Commission, 2023). The EU transport policy aims at reducing road transport towards less polluting and more energy efficient modes of transport. The ‘Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy’ plan (European Commission, 2020) aims to a more sustainable, green, smart and resilient mobility. The plan outlines how various transportation methods can work together to achieve these goals. Ultimately, the goal is to cut emissions by 90% by 2050, while making the transportation system smarter, more competitive, safer, easier to access and still affordable.

Multimodal freight transport (MFT) refers to using at least two different modes of transport (among road, rail, sea, and air) in a journey to move goods from one point to another with the particularity of moving of goods across global supply chains under a single contract. By optimizing routes and minimizing handling, it provides a comprehensive and cost-effective approach to international trade. Goods can be transported in various transportation units (crates, pallets, cages, containers) or as loose packages loaded directly on transportation means, such as vehicles, vessels, aircrafts (Archetti et al., 2022). Despite its proved benefits, MFT has not gained a substantial share so far, due to different barriers that can be related to different issues such as regulations, delivery characteristics and interoperability (Karam et al., 2023).

In recent decades, automation has brought radical changes in many different fields, including transportation, creating major opportunities but also initiating new challenges (De Alwis and Nam, 2024) and introducing uncertainty (Dekhne et al., 2019). The growing demand for faster, more efficient, and accurate deliveries has driven the adoption of advanced technologies at all stages of the supply chain (Yang et al., 2021). The application of automation in MFT can include everything from warehouse management, package sorting and loading/unloading to route planning and autonomous vehicles. Simplifying tasks by automating non-essential processes can significantly improve operations. While automating cargo handling equipment is an important step itself for non-automated terminals, doing so while improving efficiency and not compromising, but enhancing safety, requires a more comprehensive approach.

One of the main benefits³ of the implementation of automation on MFT includes the optimization of operations, that can lead to time and cost savings (Pollehn et al., 2021), enhanced efficiency and improved resource management; it can assist decision-making and help coordination of operations and scalability of solutions. In terms of safety, automation can reduce the risk of accidents by detecting and preventing mechanical failures and

³ In addition to the literature sources used, benefits, challenges and barriers for automation presented herein were also derived from interviews conducted with partners from the AutoMoTIF consortium, who have extensive experience in the field. For more information, please see the project’s deliverable D1.1 AutoMoTIF: Playground and Vision.

by minimizing employees' exposure to hazardous situations and can provide more extensive control and better access' supervision e.g. in restricted areas of a terminal. Moreover, through automation, human errors can be eliminated and therefore higher accuracy can be achieved; in addition to that, larger volumes of data can be collected faster and with higher precision. Another critical advantage of the use of automation is the effective monitoring of the environmental impact of a terminal or hub, contributing also to raising awareness regarding the importance of limiting emissions (Evmides et al., 2024; Chu et al., 2018).

The implementation of automation has a direct impact on the workforce of the MFT industry; some restructuring may be necessary while other positions might no longer be even necessary. That makes workers often more reluctant to accept automation, as they fear that it might jeopardize their own job (Hellmuth-Sander, 2023) and calls for significant changes in the working culture of organizations, or/and for extensive training of personnel, that can be a costly and time-consuming process (Baimukhanbetova et al., 2023). The high initial investment that might be required for physical and digital infrastructure in order for the automation to work, is often another barrier faced by organizations that are willing to experiment with innovative technologies (Institute of Supply Chain Management, 2024), especially when many times a considerable amount of time is required until a noteworthy return on investment is perceived. Another barrier that needs to be overcome when automation is under discussion is the lack of compatibility between existing systems and new automated technologies. High reliance on automated systems can raise concerns about vulnerability to technical failures and the collection and analysis of real-time data can have implications on privacy and data security, due to vulnerability to potential cyber-attacks (Evmides et al., 2024; Chu et al., 2018). Cybersecurity is thus becoming an increasingly critical domain for supply chains (Jeong, 2024).

Ensuring interoperability among different automated processes is an additional key challenge, as inadequate data standardization can impede effective communication and coordination. Automated systems can be versatile enough to accommodate different handling requirements, for instance for cargo that is not transferred by containers. In the field of MFT, many different stakeholders with diverse backgrounds, aspirations and objectives are involved, therefore involving them in every step of the planning and implementation process of introducing automation can be particularly challenging. Last not least, interpreting the regulatory and legal framework can pose extra challenges when automation is involved, and new frameworks or modifications of the existing ones might be required before proceeding (Evmides et al., 2024; Chu et al., 2018).

Emerging technologies play a crucial role in the introduction and implementation of automated processes, and it through them that automation is being materialized and gaining potential. Several emerging technologies are being used in different applications in the field of freight transport and logistics, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), big data analytics, blockchain (Pesquera, 2024), 5G networks, automated vehicles, automated robot cranes, smart warehousing solutions and advanced traffic management systems.

The concept of a Digital Twin (DT) is another emerging technology, the application of which in logistical environments, such as ports and intermodal terminals, has advanced significantly in recent years (Liu et al., 2024). Initially envisioned as basic digital models for visualization and planning, DTs have evolved into sophisticated systems capable of monitoring, simulating, and optimizing operations in real-time (Le and Fan, 2024). It refers to a virtual replica of a physical asset, system, or process that captures data from sensors and

IoT devices to reflect the state, history, and behaviour of its physical counterpart (Javaid et al., 2023). While DT technology incorporates real-time data (Attaran et al., 2023), this is not a fundamental requirement in all cases; their key characteristic is the ability to collect, store, and manage data to support simulations, predictive analysis, and prescriptive modelling. This flexible approach enables DTs to operate both with real-time and buffered or historical data, depending on the specific application requirements.

The efficiency gained with the use of the DT technologies is primarily due to the ability to simulate various operational scenarios, allowing stakeholders to identify bottlenecks and optimize resource allocation without disrupting actual operations. The evolution of Digital Twins can be classified into four stages of technological maturity, each representing an increase in system interoperability, scalability, and autonomy: a) basic digital representation, b) enhanced digital representation, c) connected digital twin, d) autonomous digital twin. The four DT levels and their relationship with the proposed open reference architecture are further discussed in the next section.

The AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture Framework for Digital Twins

The rapid evolution of DT technology has brought significant advancements, but it has also introduced new challenges that must be addressed in today's era of open and modular systems. As DTs transition from closed architecture items to scalable, interoperable solutions, the complexity of managing diverse data sources, integrating legacy systems, and enabling advanced functionalities has grown exponentially (Klar, 2024). In the current era, characterized by the demand for interoperability, modularity, and scalability, organizations face critical challenges when building and managing DTs (PierNext, 2020) such as integration of diverse systems, scalability to meet expanding needs, customization for domain-specific requirements and ensuring security and data governance. To address these challenges, a new open digital twin reference architecture framework is developed in the context of the AutoMoTIF project.

The framework provides a structured and modular approach to designing DTs that meet the demands of interoperability and scalability while also offering a foundation for future advancements. By focusing on three key layers, namely, external integration, core functionality, and intermediary integration mechanisms, this architecture ensures a seamless flow of data and operations between external systems and the DTs' internal components (McKee, 2023).

The Open Reference Architecture is specifically designed to overcome the limitations of traditional closed systems, which are often difficult to expand, providing a framework that is modular, interoperable, and expandable, enabling the seamless integration of external components, tools, and technologies from various providers. This openness does not imply that the system is "free" or unregulated; instead, it refers to the system's ability to interoperate with diverse external modules while maintaining a standardized core (Klar et al., 2024). In this context, the core attributes of an open architecture for DTs are the following: modularity, interoperability, scalability, vendor independence and future-proofing. Following those principles, the Open Reference Architecture for DTs has been designed as shown in the diagram of Figure 1. Each layer addresses the challenges of being modular, interoperable, scalable, and future-ready. This ensures organizations can build robust, adaptable solutions that remain relevant in an ever-evolving technological landscape.

Figure 1 - Diagram of the AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture Framework for Digital Twins

The architecture is structured into three primary layers, each with distinct roles and functionalities:

- Outer Layer: Integration and Interoperability with External Systems

This layer is focused on connecting the DT to external systems and data sources. It defines the interfaces and mechanisms required to achieve seamless integration and data exchange with these external entities. The five main external components highlighted in this layer are AI models, simulation engines, data sources, client applications and legacy systems.

- Middle Layer: Core integration and communication functionalities

The middle layer acts as the integration and communication bridge between the external layer and the internal core. It includes the fundamental services and tools necessary for data processing, transformation, and communication. It is essential for enabling interoperability, as it standardizes the flow of information and operations between the external systems and the internal components.

- Inner layer: Core functionalities of the Digital Twin

At the heart of the architecture lies the core functionality layer, which encompasses the essential components that define the capabilities of any Digital Twin. This layer provides the foundational capabilities that enable a Digital Twin to function effectively, including simulation, optimization, prediction, and decision-making.

The architecture's design ensures that all three layers work harmoniously to deliver a comprehensive, interoperable, and scalable Digital Twin. Its modular nature allows for the independent upgrading and replacement of components, while its interoperability ensures seamless integration with diverse systems. Additionally, its scalability supports growth and the integration of advanced functionalities as technology evolves. By adopting this reference architecture, organizations can build Digital Twins that are not only capable of real-time monitoring and optimization but also adaptable to future advancements and operational needs. This approach empowers organizations to build flexible systems at early stages that can grow in complexity, achieve

full interoperability and autonomy at the highest levels, leverage cutting-edge technologies to optimize operational efficiency, enhance decision-making, and maximize scalability.

The Open Architecture Framework serves as a critical enabler for the four AutoMoTIF use cases described in the following section, where it guides the implementation of essential functionalities in port automation, logistics optimization, and real-time visualization. By supporting seamless integration with IoT devices, AI models, simulation engines, and legacy systems, the architecture provides the tools needed to achieve greater levels of automation and decision-making efficiency. Through its scalability, the AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture ensures that these use cases can progressively activate and expand functionalities as they move towards higher levels of Digital Twin maturity. It lays the foundation for transforming port operations, streamlining logistics networks, and enhancing supply chain visibility, aligning each use case with the maturity progression and interoperability focus of each of the four DT levels (see previous section).

AutoMoTIF Use Cases

Definition and scope

- Use Case 1: Automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels

Use Case (UC) 1 focuses on investigating the potential advantages of utilizing automation across all phases of the port call process in terms of operational efficiency, safety, and environmental impact. This includes the vessel's arrival at the port, which encompasses the initial announcement, allocation of berth windows as well as the tugboats assignment. The process continues with the vessel's manoeuvring and docking, both performed by the assigned tugboats, followed by the stevedoring operations that secure the vessel on the quay to initiate the cargo loading and unloading processes. The undocking and manoeuvring of the vessel as it departs from the port is also included in UC1.

The overall aim of the UC is to identify the basic requirements for a seamless automated port call process. To achieve this objective, UC1 will simulate the entire process of berthing and unberthing at a generic port (i.e. container terminal), to replicate the complex interactions among the process key players with the assumption that the operation will be performed by fully autonomous tugboats (i.e., without a master onboard) and that an Automated Mooring System is installed at the quay. The simulation will incorporate various key parameters for the process, such as weather conditions, size of the vessel, number of tugboats, significant wave etc.

- Use Case 2: Automated port operations

Use Case 2 focuses on exploring the benefits of automating port terminal processes through simulation, using real-world data from the Port of Bilbao, Spain. It will integrate historical data with a simulation model to replicate current baseline operations performance with aspirations of being compared to its automated counterpart. Hence, the simulation will assess various operational objectives, showcasing how automation might affect different aspects of the terminal such as vessel handling, cargo operations, vehicle flow, and logistics efficiency. By simulating these scenarios, UC2 aims to identify an optimal configuration of the terminal operations that reduces inefficiencies, lowers environmental impact, and enhances synchronization within the logistics chain.

The aim of the UC is to provide the port with a simulation environment that allows it to assess any economic and/or execution time benefits of applying certain automation to its logistics processes, without incurring the costs and inconveniences of carrying out a real feasibility test on-site. Among the variety of activities that take place in port terminal operations, this use case will focus on the operations encompassing from the arrival of the vessel to the storage of the cargo, simulating the following main processes: loading and unloading, transfer of cargo to the warehouse, cargo handling and shunting operations and warehouse operations.

- Use Case 3: Automated shunting as a service-oriented platform

Use Case 3 explores the implementation of autonomous technologies on an inland terminal dedicated to intermodal freight, focusing on optimizing current and future operational flows at the Magli Intermodal Service (MIS) terminal in Brescia, Italy. The terminal has a complex and constraining layout; it is currently undergoing expansion and, within 10 years, will feature a significantly larger infrastructure. The UC's scope includes simulating the terminal's anticipated layout and operations to assess the potential impact of automation in handling the expected traffic. This approach replicates the terminal's current and future configurations and provides a comprehensive representation of anticipated operations. By incorporating potential operating procedures that have not been implemented, it enables an exploration of how automation may enhance the terminal's efficiency, adaptability, and overall capability to meet evolving demands. Furthermore, simulating automation allows to introduce the optimization of features that are inherently connected with autonomous solutions.

UC3 aims to evaluate and advance the implementation of automation in intermodal freight transport. Studying the introduction of automation using simulations for both the current and future terminal setups allows for a detailed comparison of its effectiveness in different scenarios, highlighting potential benefits and challenges. By simulating these operations, critical factors that influence efficiency can be identified and addressed early, ensuring the terminal is well-prepared for future demands. Notably, many roles and equipment required in the future are not yet in place, presenting an opportunity to avoid some common setbacks associated with automation. This can be achieved by investing directly in the appropriate equipment, personnel training, and developing best practices, while designing process flows from the ground up.

- Use Case 4: Automated multimodal terminal operations

Use Case 4 employs a simulation model to evaluate the impact of a new automated intermodal terminal design, featuring the Autonomous Wagon Train (AWT) concept to improve cargo movement between different transport modes, on the Northern Terminal Bremerhaven GmbH in Germany. Terminals require faster, more seamless cargo transfers between rail, road, and sea transport to keep up with growing logistics demands. By allowing autonomous wagons to directly interact with Automated Straddle Carriers (ASCs), the automation not only enhances operational efficiency but also paves the way for smarter, more sustainable intermodal terminal operations. This system represents a leap forward in logistics technology, promising substantial improvements in speed, cost, and safety for container terminals. The simulation will take current traffic conditions as input to assess the effectiveness of this innovative approach.

UC4 aims to provide an overview of the impact of applying innovative automation technologies on the operational efficiency of an intermodal terminal. To achieve this, simulation models will be used with two terminal designs, considering combinations of alternative traffic flows. Moreover, the UC will provide input on the requirements for implementing yard automation technologies to optimize the efficiency of the terminal's multimodal operations, enhance sustainability, and reduce environmental footprint.

User needs and technological gaps

The following table (Table 1) presents a summary of the key user needs identified for the four AutoMoTIF use cases. The needs were co-defined with the users (actors involved) in each use case, following interviews with the respective project's partners and external stakeholders. As the table reveals, these are both operational as well as management needs, and while there are similarities among the use cases (e.g. eliminating delays and having access to real-time monitoring, enhancing safety), there are specific tailored-made needs that emerged for each use case, which will be taken into account for shaping the technical specifications of the simulation models, after translating these needs into functional and non-functional requirements.

Table 1 Key user needs for the four AutoMoTIF Use Cases

UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4
Minimize delays	Optimize and coordinate loading/unloading	Fast and Reliable Automated Coupling/Decoupling Systems	Efficient cargo transfer between modes
Improve safety	Material inspection	Precision in Wagon Positioning for Sequential Shunting Tasks	Flexibility in cargo management
Minimize port emissions	Shunting operations	Reduction of Wagon Coupling and Decoupling Time	Predictive maintenance for equipment
Real-time process monitoring	Cargo transfer	Energy Optimization During Automated Shunting Movements	Minimized waiting times for vehicles
Provision of 24/7 port services	Resource allocation	Automation of routinary tasks	Accurate real-time information
	Event scheduling	Efficient Track Allocation for High-Volume	Increased safety standards
	Dynamic decision support	Optimized Resource Allocation	Environmental sustainability
	Synchronization	Real-Time Operational Overview	
		Compliance with Automated Safety	

Table 2 presents key technological gaps related to the integration of automation that have been identified for each use case. Recognizing the existence of these gaps is essential for stakeholders aiming to improve efficiency,

safety and reliability.

Table 2 Key technological gaps for the four AutoMoTIF Use Cases

UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4
Continuous process monitoring (unmanned tugs)	Monitoring	Automation Limitations	Lack of comprehensive automation for transfers
Interaction of autonomous tugboats with conventional vessels & tugboats	Software challenges	Interoperability Issues	Data integration
Data exchange rate and management	Data integration consistency and management	Data utilization challenges	Limited infrastructure for long trains
Cyber security issues	Infrastructure limitations	Scalability Concerns	Lack of standardized interfaces between systems
	Demand forecasting	Limited Predictive Capabilities	Low precision of current sensing systems
		Insufficient User Training Resources	

Conclusions

Automation in multimodal freight transport and logistics has emerged as a promising way to address some of the most crucial challenges faced by the sector, including capacity constraints, environmental concerns and the growing demand for faster and more efficient delivery of goods and services. The research presented herein opens interesting pathways towards achieving seamless integration of automated processes across the end-to-end logistics chain using different transport modes. This requires a shift in the direction of integrated and interoperable systems, real-time data-sharing, and harmonized workflows that connect every link in the logistics chain. The AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture Framework for Digital Twins provides a robust foundation for this transformation to a more interconnected logistics ecosystem, by offering a roadmap for stakeholders to bridge existing technological gaps and address successfully relevant user needs. The proposed framework can be used as a blueprint for integrating and optimizing automation across various use cases towards future-proof multimodal logistics systems. The modular design of the reference architecture allows it to scale across use cases, in order to reflect the increasing complexity of logistics operations. Further steps in the context of the AutoMoTIF project will include the deployment of the four use cases, building synergies among them and overcoming boundaries, and ultimately investigating how all use cases could work together under the umbrella of the open reference architecture framework.

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